

MEMBRANE STRESS DISTRIBUTIONS
IN POST-BUCKLED COMPOSITE PLATES
WITH CIRCULAR HOLES

I.H Marshall
W. Little
M.M El-Tayeb

Department of Mechanical and Production Engineering
Paisley College of Technology
High Street, Paisley, PA1 2BE

ABSTRACT

Herein is contained the results of an extensive theoretical and experimental investigation into the changes in membrane stress levels in the vicinity of central circular holes in thin rectangular planform, composite plates as progressive post buckling loading is applied. Both rectangular and square plates with simply supported edges are considered.

It is clearly shown that marked changes in the aforementioned membrane stress distribution take place as plate buckling is initiated, with considerable load shedding to the plate edges of increasing magnitude as post buckling progresses. This phenomenon is theoretically predicted and experimentally verified in both isotropic and composite perforated plates.

INTRODUCTION

To date a vast number of papers have been published on the buckling of platemwork structures, covering a wide variety of plate geometries, loading conditions, boundary conditions and material properties. Indeed it would be true to say that the phenomenon of elastic buckling of plates is, with the exception of some relatively specialised problems, readily understood and capable of analytical study. However, although an increasing number of papers dealing with composite plates have become available, most of this work has been restricted to plates with isotropic material properties. Although historically the study of isotropic materials is understandable, the last few decades have seen an unprecedented interest in composites as viable structural materials. These new materials are not simply lightweight alternatives to traditional metallic materials of construction, rather they possess unique structural

properties hitherto unobtainable. Indeed many of man's greatest achievements would not have been possible save for composite materials, i.e. the space shuttle.

Notwithstanding earlier comment on the prevalence of isotropic plate buckling studies a considerable number of equivalent studies concerned with composite materials have been published, with a discernable increase in numbers in recent years. A notable precis of work on composite plate buckling is contained in (1) and recently in (2).

Amongst the problems cited in (1) which have received little attention, either experimentally or theoretically is the effects of holes or cut-outs on the buckling and post-buckling stability of rectangular planform composite plates. In view of the inevitability of access holes in many structural situations the problem was deemed worthy of study by the authors. Although not exhaustive, references (3) to (14) give a flavour of work to date on the stability of isotropic plates with holes. Likewise (15) to (22) give an indication of recent work on composite plates with holes.

THEORETICAL INVESTIGATION

2. Since a number of aspects of the authors analytical study of the buckling and post buckling uniaxially compressed thin orthotropic, rectangular planform plates with central circular holes have been adequately covered in (17) (18) (19) (20) and theoretical aspects of the membrane stress distributions will be the subject of a future paper, in the interests of brevity, only theoretical predictions will be contained herein.

2.1 Boundary Conditions

With reference to Figure 1 the plate boundary conditions can be stated as:

$$\text{along edges } x = \pm A/2$$

$$\omega = 0$$

$$\frac{\delta^2 \omega}{\delta x^2} + \nu_y \frac{\delta^2 \omega}{\delta y^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\delta^2 F}{\delta y^2} = 0$$

$$\frac{\delta^2 F}{\delta x \delta y} = 0$$

$$y = \pm B/2$$

$$\omega = 0$$

$$\frac{\delta^2 \omega}{\delta y^2} + \nu_x \frac{\delta^2 \omega}{\delta x^2} = 0$$

$$\nu = \text{constant}$$

$$\frac{\delta^2 F}{\delta x \delta y} = 0$$

at the hole boundary

$$M_r \Big|_{r=r_0} = 0$$

$$\left[Q_r - \frac{\partial M_{r\theta}}{r \partial \theta} \right]_{r=r_0} = 0$$

i.e. stress free hole boundary.

The loaded edges will be assumed to be subject to constant edge displacement throughout the range of loading. It should be noted that this is in contrast to some complementary investigations which have considered constant edge stresses to be incrementally applied (15) (22). Figure 2 shows that these fundamentally different loading conditions induce significantly different buckling responses in square isotropic plates, particularly at high hole diameter/plate width ratios. It can be shown that the same characteristics are exhibited by equivalent composite plates.

Figure 1. - THE PLATE CO-ORDINATES AND DIMENSIONS

2.2 Pre-Buckling Stresses

At this stage it may be beneficial to compare the present theoretical predictions with the available isotropic results. Figure 3 shows a comparison between the work of PRADHAM (23) and HOWLAND (24) and the

Figure 2 -

BUCKLING OF ISOTROPIC SQUARE PLATES
- DIFFERENT LOADING CONDITIONS

Figure 3 -

PRE-BUCKLING STRESS CONCENTRATION AT
HOLE BOUNDARY OF ISOTROPIC PLATES

Figure 4 - PRE-BUCKLING STRESS DISTRIBUTION OF ISOTROPIC SQUARE PLATES

Figure 5 - EFFECT OF DEGREE OF ORTHOTROPY ON MAXIMUM STRESS AT HOLE BOUNDARY.

authors theoretical predictions for the stress concentration factors at the maximum stress position on the hole boundary for a range of hole diameter width plate.

A further insight into the distribution of stress at the plate minimum cross-section for a range of hole diameter/plate widths is given in Figure 4, again for isotropic plates. Clearly the 'finite' plate with a hole displays markedly different tendencies from the 'infinite' equivalent.

In the case of composite plates with orthotropic material characteristics the theoretical work curves of PRADHAM (23) are compared with some finite predictions by the authors, Figure 5. As expected the elastic stiffness ratio (E_y/E_x) has a pronounced effect on the stress concentration levels for the range of plate geometries considered.

EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

3. In view of the relative dearth of published work on the buckling of perforated plates, particularly papers dealing with either experimental studies or post-buckling problems, an extensive test programme was initiated. To date in excess of 600 plates with a variety of geometries have been tested to determine their buckling and post-buckling characteristics.

The isotropic plates tested were manufactured using aluminium, galvanised steel and chopped strand glass/polyester resin. A range of unidirectionally reinforced glass/polyester resin plates with orthotropic material properties have also been tested.

Figure 6 shows a typical composite plate with an array of electrical resistance strain gauges used to experimentally monitor the distribution of membrane stress at a range of applied edge compressions.

Since the test rig has been adequately described in (17) and a further paper will deal at length with experimental aspects of the present investigation, for reasons of brevity no further elaboration will be contained herein.

Figure 6 - TYPICAL STRAIN GAUGED COMPOSITE PLATE

4.1 Isotropic Plates ($\lambda = 2.0$)

At this stage, in view of earlier comments regarding the scarcity of published work on the stability of plates with holes, particularly composite plates, it was considered prudent to compare the results with the isotropic work of RITCHIE (10). Figure 7 reassuringly shows that the present theory and experiments compares well with his results. It is interesting to note the significant changes in membrane stresses which take place as progressive post-buckling is initiated, indicating a substantial shedding of load to the plate sides.

4.2 Composite Square Plates ($\lambda = 1.0$)

The equivalent problem for composite square plates is considered in Figure 8. Once again significant load shedding from the central region to the plate side as progressive post-buckling loads are applied is visible, with theory and experiment reasonably in accord.

However at larger hole diameter/plate widths a different tendency is discernable with high membrane stress levels at the hole boundary tending to have far greater significance. Moreover, the present theoretical predictions are shown to have diminishing accuracy at high post buckling

Figure 7 - RELATIVE MEMBRANE STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN ISOTROPIC RECTANGULAR PLATES D/A = 0.2

Figure 8 - RELATIVE MEMBRANE STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN ORTHOTROPIC SQUARE PLATES D/A = 0.2

Figure 9

RELATIVE MEMBRANE STRESS DISTRIBUTION IN
ORTHOTROPIC SQUARE PLATES $D/A = 0.4$

loads. Since the present theory has, of necessity, a number of analytical approximations this is not unreasonable. However, for the "useful" range of loading, theory and experiments are shown to compare well.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The present theoretical techniques have been shown to compare well with the available isotropic work and the experimental results reported herein, with some loss of accuracy at high post-buckling loads noticeable.

The present work gives a useful insight into the phenomenon of increased buckling loads of plates with high diameter/plate widths over their unperforated counterparts i.e. the effects of load shedding from the hole vicinity to the relatively well supported side regions.

It has been clearly shown that the membrane stress distribution at the plate minimum cross-section is greatly influenced by the hole diameter/plate width ratio and the degree of instant orthotropy.

At nominal hole diameter/plate width ratios the peak membrane stresses occur at the unloaded edges, thereby indicating a vicinity of possible failure. Whereas at higher ratios the hole boundary is the critical region with respect to membrane stresses. This is in accord with "traditional" engineering concepts of stress concentration factors near discontinuities.

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A, B	Plate Dimensions
D	Hole Diameter
P	Applied Compressive Load
$BL(UNP)$	Buckling Load of Equipment Unperforated Plate
F	Airy Stress Function
M_r	Radial Bending Moment
Q_r	Radial Shear Force
$M_{r\theta}$	Radial Twisting Moment
v	Applied Constant Edge Displacement
w	Plate Lateral Deflection
x, y	Co-ordinates
r, r_0	Hole Co-ordinates
δ_{ym}	Applied Edge Membrane Stress
$\delta_Y(UNP)$	Applied Edge Membrane Stress in Equivalent Unperforated Plate.
λ	Plate aspect ratio = B/A